

Accelerated Vermicomposting of Kitchen Waste Using Tamarind Waste Liquid: Implications for Sustainable Organic Waste Management

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Abstract

This study evaluated the effect of tamarind waste liquid as a bio-catalytic additive during vermicomposting of kitchen waste using *Eisenia andrei*. Kitchen waste, cow dung, and sawdust were mixed in a 5:4:1 ratio and pre-decomposed for 7 days before vermicomposting for 30 days. Tamarind waste liquid was applied on alternate days to maintain moisture and enhance microbial activity, while a control was maintained without the additive. Physico-chemical parameters were monitored on days 0, 15, and 30. The amended treatment showed faster stabilization, marked by a decline in temperature from 33.16 to 27.4°C, substantial reductions in volatile solids (71.68% to 43.73%), total organic carbon (39.16% to 23.89%), BOD (320 to 40.54 mg/L), and COD (528.11 to 161.7 mg/L). Nutrient enrichment was also observed, with total Kjeldahl nitrogen increasing from 1.64% to 2.53%, potassium from 2.48% to 3.18%, and phosphorus from 1.03% to 1.47%. The final compost showed a reduced C/N ratio, indicating maturity and stability, compared with the control. Overall, tamarind waste liquid improved degradation efficiency, accelerated compost maturation, and enhanced nutrient quality, demonstrating its potential as a value-added amendment for sustainable kitchen waste management and vermicompost production.

Keywords: Bio-additive, vermicomposting, kitchen waste, *Eisenia andrei*.

1. Introduction

The rapid increase in solid waste generation, driven by the surge in rising Urban population, the new-age consumer base and evolving consumption patterns, has positioned India among the top contributors to global waste output highlighting the urgent need for sustainable and decentralized waste management strategies. According to recent estimates, India produces approximately 0.7 kg of solid waste per capita per day, with kitchen waste constituting a significant proportion—accounting for over 45% of total food waste, surpassing 78 million tonnes annually (Priya et al. 2023).

A significant proportion of this biodegradable kitchen waste, largely generated in urban regions, despite its high resource recovery potential, remains grossly underutilized due to inadequate segregation, collection inefficiencies, and improper disposal methods such as open dumping and burning (Roy et al. 2024). Such practices result in the uncontrolled emission of greenhouse gases such as methane, thereby accelerating environmental degradation, including air, soil, and groundwater pollution (Rathod et al. 2024). The growing urgency to manage kitchen waste sustainably has emphasized the need for decentralized, low-cost, and eco-friendly treatment solutions (Sharma et al. 2024).

Among the available technologies, and various organic treatment methods, vermicomposting has emerged as an eco-friendly and efficient biological process that utilizes earthworms, particularly species such as *Eisenia andrei*, and associated microbial communities to transform organic waste into a stable, nutrient-enriched end product known as vermicompost (Kumari et al. 2024). The non-thermophilic, bio-oxidative process not only enhances nutrient mineralization/bioavailability, but also improves physical parameters such as porosity and increased water-holding capacity of the compost (Celik et al. 2021).

In this process, kitchen waste like vegetable peels and fruit scraps, etc. acts as the primary source of nutrients, while amendments such as cow dung, dry leaves, or rock phosphate are added to improve the nutritional content, maturity, and stability of the final compost. Unlike traditional composting, vermicomposting operates under milder conditions and produces compost with significantly lower C:N ratios, higher bioavailability of nutrients, and reduced phytotoxicity, making it a valuable soil amendment for sustainable agricultural and horticultural applications (Ahmad et al. 2021). Despite its many advantages, a major limitation of vermicomposting is the relatively longer processing time it takes due to variability in compost quality which depends on substrate composition and environmental conditions. The processing time often extends up to 75–100 days (Garg et al. (2006), (Bharadwaj 2010)). To address these constraints, recent studies have emphasized on the use of organic additives or co-substrates such as cow dung, sawdust, and agricultural residues to enhance microbial activity, speeding up decomposition and optimize the nutrient balance and moisture content within the substrate (Chaudhary et al. 2024).

Furthermore, liquid organic waste amendments, particularly those rich in organic acids and micronutrients, have shown considerable potential in accelerating decomposition and optimizing the vermicomposting process (Qi et al. 2022). Biological additives are microorganisms that are incorporated into a composting or vermicomposting pile to aid in ammonia assimilation or breakdown of lignocellulosic substrate (Barthod et al. 2018). The choice of additives used for vermiculture, is often influenced by their potential adverse effects on the development of earthworms. Bacteria with the genera *Bacillus*, *Lactobacillus*,

Alcaligenes, *Enterococcus*, and *Clostridium* is commercially popular. These additives can improve leaching, release of gases, aeration, and nutrient content in the final product. Composting additives can modify the microbial community, influencing aeration, temperature, moisture content, pH, and nutrient availability (Noor et al. 2024). Organic additives include residual straws, well-decomposed manure, green waste crushed pieces of wood, stubbles, dried stems, and leaves. Biochar has gained popularity as a stable organic component for composting and vermicomposting (Sabzehmeidani et al. 2021).

Bio enzymes represent an optimal and sustainable option for improving the composting of both domestic and agricultural waste. Apart from being a natural, safe and inert liquid enzyme formulation derived from plant extracts, it is incombustible in nature and plays a big role in enhancing soil properties and boosting stability (Gattupalli et al. 2024) of enzymes, known as Garbage Enzymes (GE), obtained from discarded vegetables and fruits. These enzymes, when activated during the composting process, offer various advantages, particularly by accelerating decomposition and enhancing the quality of the compost. Such enzymes are effective biocatalysts for enhancing compost quality, retaining nitrogen, and lowering the emission of ammonia during composting (Gattupalli et al. 2024).

Inorganic additives include lime, clays, and manufacturing wastes such as fly ash. Because of their ability to adsorb heavy metals both chemically and physically, minerals like zeolite and Ca-bentonite were widely used, in purification systems of water and soil (Wang et al. 2016). Vermicomposting occasionally involves the addition of these minerals.

From amongst underexplored additives, one such additive that stands out is tamarind waste liquid, a by-product formed during tamarind pulp extraction. Rich in organic acids, reducing sugars, and soluble micronutrients, this liquid holds the potential to act as a bio-catalyst, to stimulate microbial metabolism, promote faster organic matter degradation, and improve nutrient release during vermicomposting. Notably, although tamarind processing industries produce substantial volumes of liquid waste in India, its application in composting systems has received limited scientific attention. Most prior studies have focused on solid co-amendments, leaving a gap in understanding the role of such liquid by-products in enhancing vermicomposting efficiency. Bio Enzymes, on the other hand, are organic substances formed by fermenting fresh vegetable/fruit waste in the presence of water and jaggery.

In order to fill this gap, the present-day study explores the integrated physico-chemical properties of vermicompost derived from kitchen waste and fortified with tamarind waste liquid. The vermicomposting process was conducted using a batch method with *Eisenia andrei* as the primary decomposer species and co-substrates which included cow dung and sawdust. Key parameters such as pH, EC, TOC, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), essential nutrients (N, P, K, Ca, Na), and heavy metals (Mn, Fe, Cu, Zn, Ni, Co) were evaluated throughout the composting process. This study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by demonstrating the feasibility of tamarind waste liquid as a potential and value-added resource for waste valorization, and by establishing the quality and applicability of the resulting vermicompost as a sustainable soil amendment.

2. Methodology

2.1 Compost production and sampling

Around 50 kg of kitchen waste (KW) was collected from nearby sources, including restaurants, the CSIR-NEERI canteen, and hostels located at CSIR-NEERI, Nagpur, Maharashtra. The collected waste was homogenized with cow dung (CD) and sawdust (SD) in a ratio of 5:4:1 (KW:CD:SD by weight). Cow dung was procured from a local dairy farm (Lava Dhaba, Nagpur), while sawdust was sourced from a nearby sawmill in Nagpur. This mixing ratio, along with the earthworm species *Eisenia andrei* and the application of tamarind waste liquid extract, was derived from an optimization study conducted in a preceding objective focusing on KW vermicomposting. The blended substrate was subjected to a 7-day pre-degradation phase to initiate microbial activity and reduce initial toxicity. Following this period, the partially decomposed substrate was transferred to the vermicomposting setup, where it was inoculated with *Eisenia andrei*. The earthworm species was obtained from Shri Sai Farm Development Services, New Delhi, India.

Approximately 1kg of earthworms (*Eisenia andrei*) were introduced into the system for the biodegradation of 50 kg of pre-decomposed organic waste, following the recommendation that earthworms consume organic matter equivalent to approximately 50% of their body weight daily (Varma and Kalamdhad 2016). A total of 22 kg of vermicompost was obtained after 30 days, which was subsequently utilized for plant growth studies. To maintain optimal moisture levels (~60–70%) within the vermireactor, a diluted solution of tamarind waste liquid was applied as a moistening agent on alternate days. The tamarind waste liquid served as a bio-catalyst, enhancing microbial activity and accelerating the vermicomposting process.

The prepared vermicompost was subjected to physicochemical and biological characterization prior to its application in the pot experiment. The vermicomposting process was carried out for a period of 30 days. Upon completion, the vermicompost was naturally dried under the sun for 1-2 days and subsequently sieved to obtain a uniform material for further analysis. Representative samples were collected from three distinct locations within the vermicomposting heap, specifically from the mid and terminal regions, following thorough mixing to ensure sample homogeneity. Composite samples were collected on days 0, 15, and 30 of the composting cycle. These samples were oven-dried at 105 ± 2 °C for 24 hours using a hot-air oven, ground, and passed through a 0.2 mm mesh sieve. The processed samples were then stored in airtight containers for subsequent physicochemical analyses. The basic characteristics of the raw material employed in the composting process are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Initial Characterisation of raw material. ($n=3$, $SD=\pm$)

Parameters	Kitchen waste (KW)	Cow-dung (CD)	WFL T	Saw-dust (SD)
Moisture content (%)	-	80.5 ± 1.1	-	11.2 ± 0.7
Volatile solids (%)	76.1 ± 1.4	89.1 ± 1.7	-	17.99 ± 2.2
Total organic carbon	43.7 ± 0.31	49.23 ± 2.1	-	10.73 ± 2.2
pH	5.49 ± 0.05	7.01 ± 0.4	3.5 ± 0.65	6.01 ± 0.8
EC (mS/cm)	1.25 ± 0.2	3.87 ± 0.08	0.99 ± 1.2	3.17 ± 0.09
Total Kjeldahl nitrogen, TKN (%)	1.37 ± 0.2	1.25 ± 0.2	1.67 ± 0.99	0.2 ± 0.07
Total phosphorus, TP (%)	0.57 ± 0.2	0.79 ± 0.09	0.22 ± 0.14	0.49 ± 0.18

Organic carbon/Nitrogen (C:N)	31.89 ± 0.18	39.38 ± 0.12	-	53.65 ± 0.01
Sodium, Na (%)	0.49 ± 0.5	0.25 ± 0.2	0.62 ± 0.99	0.09 ± 0.2
Potassium, K (%)	1.01 ± 0.18	0.89 ± 0.5	0.54 ± 0.31	0.09 ± 0.1
Calcium, Ca (%)	0.98 ± 0.09	1.14 ± 0.4	0.12 ± 0.86	0.24 ± 0.2
Manganese, Mn (mg/kg)	137.5	811.00	-	211.8
Iron, Fe (mg/kg)	70.45	365.99	-	0
Copper, Cu (mg/kg)	52.15	81.92	-	72.20
Cobalt, Co (mg/kg)	12.50	11.55	-	5.5
Zinc, Zn (mg/kg)	187.39	193.5 ± 2.14	-	98.9 ± 1.95

2.1.2 Physico-chemical, biological, and total heavy metal analyses:

The powdered compost samples were subjected to a series of physicochemical analyses (Table 3). Electrical conductivity (EC) and pH were determined by preparing a 1:10 (v/v) suspension of the sample and measuring it using a digital conductivity meter and a microprocessor-controlled pH meter, respectively. Moisture content was estimated by oven-drying the samples at 110 ± 5 °C for 24 h in a hot-air oven. For proper homogenization, the samples were shaken horizontally at 120 rpm for 2 h. Volatile solids (VS) were analyzed by combusting 5 g of sample in a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 2 h according to APHA (2017). Total organic carbon (TOC) was estimated following the method described in (Mazumdar et al. 2020), while total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) was quantified using the Kjeldahl digestion and distillation procedure as outlined in (Maturi et al. 2021). For nutrient estimation, 0.2 g of dried sample was digested using 10 mL of a di-acid mixture (H₂SO₄:HClO₄ in 5:1 ratio), and the concentrations of Na, K, and Ca were determined with a flame photometer according to EPA 3050b (1996). Total concentrations of heavy metals (Mn, Ni, Fe, Cu, Co, and Zn) were measured using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). Soluble biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and soluble chemical oxygen demand (COD) were evaluated using the Winkler titration method and the closed reflux dichromate method, respectively, following APHA (2017).

Table 2. Physico-chemical analysis of vermicompost at different interval with respect to control treatment. ($n=3$, $S. D = \pm$, VCt - Vermicompost-Tamarind, Vermicompost-control- VCc)

Parameters	VCt (Day 0)	VCt (Day 15)	VCt Day (Day 30)	Control (Day 0)	Control (Day 15)	Control (Day 30)
Temperature	33.16 ± 0.86	31.9 ± 0.1	27.4 ± 0.45	32.53 ± 0.45	32.46 ± 0.50	30.03 ± 1.02
Moisture content (%)	74.99 ± 0.94	69.15 ± 0.91	65.58 ± 0.50	75.41 ± 0.43	70.93 ± 0.89	62.55 ± 0.55
pH	6.41 ± 0.10	7.19 ± 0.15	8.59 ± 0.19	6.82 ± 0.23	6.32 ± 0.37	6.32 ± 0.27
Electrical conductivity EC (mS/cm)	2.06 ± 0.41	2.53 ± 0.05	3.10 ± 0.25	1.32 ± 0.56	1.65 ± 0.06	1.76 ± 0.26

Volatile solid VS%	71.68±0.58	59.35±1.19	43.73±0.9	84.8±0.69	78.80±0.58	78.18±0.74
Total organic carbon TOC%	39.16±0.32	32.43±0.65	23.89±0.5 1	46.33±0.37	43.06±0.32	42.72±0.40
Total Kjeldhal Nitrogen TKN%	1.64±0.04	1.9±2.53	2.53±0.35	1.41±0.04	1.44±0.10	1.53±0.01
Total Potassium TK%	2.48±0.44	3.14±0.07	3.18±0.04	1.37±0.15	1.25±0.02	1.34±0.01
Total Phosphorus TP%	1.03±0.19	1.04±0.05	1.47±0.12	0.29±0.02	0.31±0.01	0.39±0.03
Carbon/Nitrogen C/N	23.87	17.06	9.442	32.85	29.90	27.92
Biological oxygen demand BOD	320±1.34	223±1.06	40.54±0.5 9	477.12±0.5 8	262.76±0.6 7	89.85±0.78
Chemical Oxygen demand COD	528.11±0.96	324.10±0.85	161.7±0.82	599.12±0.93	336.49±0.58	220.80±0.49
Sodium (%)	0.28 ±0.07	0.64 ±0.92	0.97±0.45	0.20 ±0.05	0.33±1.03	0.530±0.68
Calcium (%)	0.36 ±0.11	0.43±0.57	0.89 ±1.22	0.31 ±0.1	0.44±1.02	0.69 ±1.72
Manganese (mg/kg)	124.41	132.06	148.2	104.49	111.02	83.35
Iron (mg/kg)	502.77	512.89	576.20	411.41	498.90	560.02
Copper (mg/kg)	81.85	82.09	92.78	78.41	89.80	120.81
Cobalt (mg/kg)	10.12	12.67	18.60	9.10	17.67	24.50

Zinc (mg/kg)	67.78	70.11	74.40	70.41	78.16	84.71
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3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Temperature Dynamics

For the determination of the level of degradation kinetics and understanding the mechanism of vermicomposting, temperature contributes substantially to the entire process. Two setups were made for vermicomposting process. Pile 1 and 2 had its temperature measured from 3 different location on 0, 15th and 30th day until the temperature dropped to optimum level the vermicompost-tamarind (VCt) from 33.16 (Day 0) to 31.9°C (Day 15) and further to 27.4°C (Day 30). while the the vermicompost- control (VCc) showed a parallel but less pronounced decline from 32.53°C to 30.03°C. A key indicator of compost maturity and microbial activity is the change in Temperature. The temperature rose sharply at first and then dropped to ambient levels, signalling stabilization of food waste and rice bran vermicomposting. (Jayakumar et al. 2023). Rapid microbial oxidation of readily degradable organics is responsible for the initial elevated temperature, which then steadily decreased as decomposition stabilized. The change from the active breakdown phase to the mesophilic stabilization phase, suits *Eisenia andrei* activity. Vermicomposting of kitchen waste and cow manure showed comparable mesophilic temperature profiles (25°C –30°C). (Zhang et al. 2024; Wu et al. 2024).

Figure 1. Changes in temperature profile during vermicomposting process.

3.2 pH and Electrical conductivity [pH and EC]

During different stages of studies (0, 15 and 30 days) the pH ratio of the vermicompost was determined from samples. During the process of vermicomposting, pH levels increased from 6.41 to 7.19, ultimately reaching 8.59 at Day 30, whereas the control remained near neutral (6.32–6.82). This rise is linked to the breakdown of organic matter and the formation of ammonium ions (NH_4^+), which raise the pH. The microbial activity during the process of Vermicomposting is influenced significantly by pH. All treatments-maintained pH values in

optimum range 7.0-8 for Agronomy (Lei et al. 2024). Furthermore, microbial metabolism flourishes at pH 7.5-8.5, facilitating excellent compost stabilization. Also, Similar dynamics have been seen in the vermicomposting of kitchen waste mixed with cow dung and biochar, where ongoing shift towards alkalinity is caused by the breakdown of organic acids and the release of carbonates. (Katiyar et al. 2023; Hasan et al. 2024).

The Electrical conductivity of a vermicompost is influenced by the type of feedstock used. Throughout the VC process, it was observed that all trials' EC values elevated. The observed EC values were 2.06 ± 0.41 , 2.53 ± 0.05 , 3.10 ± 0.25 [for 0,15th and 30th day] mS/cm for the vermicompost-tamarind (VCt) while it was on lower side for control the vermicompost-control (VCc) (Figure 2). The total EC levels in the earthworm-inoculated units fell below 4 dSm-1 threshold that is thought to be sufficient for VC to be utilized in agricultural applications. (Alavi et al. 2017). As per (Gong et al. 2017), Additives like rhamnolipid biosurfactant and microbial inoculants (*Azotobacter chroococcum* and *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*) enhanced microbial activity leading to optimized EC values in final vermicompost.

Figure. 2. Changes in (a)pH and (b)Electrical conductivity (EC) during vermicomposting process.

3.3 Volatile solid and Total Organic Carbon [VS and TOC]

In contrast to vermicompost-tamarind (VCt), which had final VS and TOC of 43.73% and 23.89%, vermicompost-control (VCc) had final VS and TOC of 78.18% and 42.72%, respectively (Figure 3). The decomposition of readily organic matter throughout vermicomposting is driven by cellulose, hemicellulose and proteins, among other early degradable components. Microbes utilize the rest of the 30% of carbon as structural components for their cellular growth after converting 60–70% of total carbon into CO₂ (Kumar et al. 2023; Poblete et al. 2022). Due to the addition of tamarind waste liquid, which probably increased microbial activity and earthworm metabolism with accelerated breakdown of organic matter, the revised treatment showed a greater fall in organic carbon decomposition. Similar results were reported by (Hussain et al. 2018) where vermicomposting of kitchen waste and paddy straw using earthworm consortium intensified the process. The rate of organic carbon, C/N ration declined signalling maturity and stabilization of the compost. The study reported by (Srivastava et al. 2020) of MSW (Municipal Solid Waste) utilizing cow dung as a additive demonstrated significant decline in TOC in mature vermicompost compared to initial waste

mixture. The enhanced VS reduction in the additive treatment with earthworm confirms that tamarind waste liquid improved microbial degradation and organic matter mineralization.

(a) (b)

Figure. 3. Changes in (a) Volatile solid (VS) and (b) Total organic carbon (TOC) during vermicomposting process.

3.4 Biological Oxygen demand and Chemical oxygen demand [BOD and COD]

The higher nutrient concentration occurs due to underlying substrate’s decomposition that are transformed to soluble, bioavailable form through mineralization. During the process BOD dropped from 320.68 mg/L to 40.55 mg/L in kitchen waste vermicomposting with tamarind waste liquid addition, whereas the control declined from 477.12 mg/L to 89.86 mg/L, suggesting improved biological decomposition in the modified treatment. Improved stability of soluble organic compounds was confirmed by the fact that COD reduced from 528.11 mg/L to 161.70 mg/L whereas the control decreased from 599.12 mg/L to 220.80 mg/L. (Rasit and Chee, 2018) studies the efficacy of liquid organic additives that was demonstrated by fermented fruit and vegetable waste-derived enzyme additives, which decreased COD and increased biodegradation efficiency during biological treatment of organic wastes. Due to the breakdown

of organic matter, BOD and COD decreased during the process (Figure 4). They also played a significant role in increasing microbial activity and oxidizing biodegradable compounds. Subsequent vermicomposting further reduced soluble organic fractions through stabilization and mineralization mediated by earthworms.

Figure. 4. Changes in (a) Biological oxygen demand (BOD) and (b) Chemical oxygen demand (COD) during vermicomposting process.

Nutrient levels (TKN, TP, Na, K, and Ca) were seen to rise during the process of vermicomposting. The increase in TKN, TK and TP were observed 1.64 to 2.53% (TKN), 2.48 to 3.18% (TK) and 1.033 to 1.47% (TP) whereas for control 1.41 to 1.53% (TKN), 1.37 to 1.34 (TK) and 0.29 to 0.39% (TP). This increase was distinct when compared to initial substrate. During the vermicomposting of biodegradable organic waste using lime and microbial inoculant as an additive the nutrient levels (TKN, TP, TK) enriched with the activity of *Bacillus polymyxa*, along with lime application which was linked to C/N ratio of initial material (Pramanik et al. 2007). This increase in the level of nutrient in the sample may be attributed by enzymes aid in the degradation of organic material and also the earthworms contributing to extra nitrogen via releasing secretory chemicals during the process. The amount of both carbon and nitrogen, two essential elements for microbial activity, determines how efficiently composting organisms with various nutritional needs are improved. The key variable influencing microbes and composting efficacy has been proposed to involve the initial C/N ratio (Birintha et al. 2020). On day 30, the vermicompost-tamarind (VCt) initial C/N ratio declined from 23.88 to 9.45, but the control vermicompost-control (VCc) group marginally lowered from 32.86 to 27.92 attributing to the acceptable limit of final Vermicompost followed by simultaneous enrichment of Nitrogen.

4. Conclusion

The study demonstrates that tamarind waste liquid is an effective additive for improving kitchen waste vermicomposting with *Eisenia andrei*. Its application enhanced microbial and earthworm-mediated decomposition, resulting in faster stabilization, greater organic matter reduction, and improved nutrient enrichment compared with the control. The treated vermicompost showed favorable maturity indicators, including lower TOC, VS, BOD, COD, and C/N ratio, along with higher TKN, TP, TK, and mineral content. These findings suggest that tamarind waste liquid can serve as a low-cost and sustainable bio-catalyst for decentralized organic waste valorization. The resulting vermicompost has strong potential as a nutrient-rich soil amendment for agricultural use. Overall, integrating tamarind waste liquid into

vermicomposting offers an innovative approach for managing both kitchen waste and agro-industrial liquid by-products while supporting circular economy and sustainable waste management goals.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Akansha Choubey: Data curation, Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Software, Validation. Anju Meshram: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Sunil Kumar: Visualization, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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